

TENSION, COMPRESSION, AND BEND PROPERTIES
FOR SiC/RBSN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The room-temperature tension, compression, and bend properties of unidirectional SiC fiber-reinforced reaction-bonded silicon nitride composites (SiC/RBSN) have been investigated. The effects of fiber content on the modulus, first matrix cracking strength, and ultimate strength properties were determined. In tension, composites with greater than 8% fiber content showed strain capability beyond matrix fracture and fiber dominated ultimate strength. In compression, the composites displayed essentially elastic behavior, and matrix-dominated ultimate strength. For both deformation modes, most mechanical properties increased with fiber content. In bend, the modulus, strength properties, and failure modes of the composites were influenced by span to thickness ratio. To avoid shear delamination, a span to thickness ratio of 20 or greater was required.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Ceramics; SiC Fiber-Reinforced Silicon Nitride; Testing/Evaluation/Characterization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Considerable interest has been shown by researchers in recent years for the development of fiber-reinforced ceramic matrix composites (FRCMC) for advanced heat engine applications. This interest stems from the fact that FRCMC can provide microstructural mechanisms for improved toughness while maintaining the advantages of monolithic ceramics, namely, high temperature strength, low density, and oxidation resistance. In addition the properties of the FRCMC can be tailored for specific applications. By choosing high strength, high modulus fibers that are compatible with the matrix and by controlling the fiber/matrix interface properties, researchers have been able to fabricate a variety of strong, tough FRCMC such as, silicon carbide fiber-reinforced reaction-bonded silicon nitride (SiC/RBSN) [1-5]. To determine the full potential of these materials for engine applications studies are needed to evaluate their deformation behavior and failure mechanisms under various stress states. Thus, the objective of

this study is to determine the deformation and fracture behavior of SiC/RBSN composites in tension, compression, and bending mode and the influence of fiber content on these properties.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material and Specimen Geometry

The composite system used in investigation consists of chemically vapor deposited SiC fiber in a porous reaction-bonded silicon nitride matrix. The starting materials for the composite fabrication were SCS-6 SiC fibers having a nominal diameter of $144\mu\text{m}$ and high purity silicon powder of an average particle size of $0.7\mu\text{m}$. The SCS-6 SiC fibers were procured from Textron Specialty Materials and the silicon powder from Union Carbide. The composites were consolidated by hot pressing and reaction-bonding methods. Details of the composite fabrication are described elsewhere [6]. The fabrication involved three steps; fabrication of fiber mats and matrix tapes, consolidation of fiber mats and silicon tapes by hot pressing, and reaction-bonding the consolidated material in a nitrogen atmosphere.

For the first step, unidirectional fiber mats were prepared by winding the fiber at desired spacing on a cylindrical mandrel, spraying a polymer fugitive binder to retain fiber spacing, and cutting the fiber preform mats into required size. For matrix tapes, silicon powder was blended with a fugitive polymer binder and then rolled into tapes of desired thickness. The selection of fiber spacing for the mats and thickness of the matrix tapes depended on the intended volume fraction of the fiber in the composite. In the second step, alternate layers of silicon tapes and fiber mats were stacked in a metal die and pressed in vacuum hot-press between 800°C to 1000°C for 1 hr at pressures between 50 to 100 MPa. In the third step, the SiC/Si preforms were heat-treated in nitrogen between 1000 to 1400°C for up to 100 hr to convert silicon to silicon nitride matrix. Typical dimensions of the nitrided panels were 125 x 50 x 2.2 mm. Composite panels containing 8-34 vol% fibers were fabricated.

To remove loose Si_3N_4 particles and smooth surface roughness, as-fabricated panels were first surface ground with a diamond impregnated metal wheel and then sliced into specimens using a cutoff blade. For tensile and compression tests, the specimen sizes were 125 x 12 x 2 mm and 125 x 6 x 2 mm, respectively. In all cases the fiber direction was parallel to the specimen length. The ends of the tensile and compression specimens were bonded with glass fiber-reinforced epoxy tabs leaving 50 and 12.5 mm, respectively, as specimen gauge lengths. The tab material was 1.04 mm thick. Each specimen was instrumented with two axial strain gauges mounted back to back at the center of the gauge section.

For three point bend testing, specimen cross-sections were similar to those of the compression specimens but the length was varied from 25 to 112 mm. The length of the specimen chosen depended on the span to thickness ratio (L/d) required. At the center of each specimen, an axial strain gauge was mounted to monitor strain.

Standard wedge grips were used for tension tests, and the IITRI fixture for compression tests [7]. All the three types of

testing were performed in an universal tensile testing at a cross-head speed of 1.26 mm/min. At least three specimens were evaluated for each test condition.

Cross-sections of as-fabricated and failed specimens were observed under optical and scanning electron microscopes.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

A representative photomicrograph of the cross-section of a 24 fiber vol% SiC/RBSN composite shown in Fig. 1 indicates the distribution of the SiC fibers in the RBSN matrix, and the substructures contained within the SiC fibers. The outer surface of the SiC fibers at the fiber/matrix interface contained a carbon-rich coating [8]. The RBSN matrix had ~ 30% interconnected porosity.

3.2 Tensile Behavior

Figure 2 shows a typical room-temperature tensile stress-strain curve for a unidirectional SiC/RBSN composite containing 24 vol% fibers. The stress-strain curve of an unreinforced RBSN matrix is also shown in the figure for comparison. The stress-strain curve of the unreinforced RBSN shows one linear region, but the composite shows three regions: two linear regions, AB and CD,

Figure. 1 A typical cross-section of a 24% SiC/RBSN composite showing fiber distribution, fiber microstructure, and matrix porosity.

Figure. 2 The tensile stress-strain curve for a 24% SiC/RBSN composite at room-temperature.

and a non-linear region, BC. The slope of the initial region AB is the primary elastic modulus. Matrix fracture occurred at the deviation from line AB. The stress level for this point is thus the first matrix cracking strength. The slope of line CD is considerably lower than that of the initial linear line, AB. Comparison of the stress-strain curves clearly indicates that reinforcement of RBSN with SiC fibers enhanced matrix fracture stress and strain capability beyond matrix fracture. These improvements in the mechanical behavior are primarily due to the higher stiffness and strength of the fibers compared to the RBSN matrix [1].

To determine mechanisms of damage accumulation during tensile deformation, specimens were loaded to different load levels, unloaded, optically observed, and then reloaded to the same original load level. Specimens previously loaded to below B, when reloaded to below, B, indicated no loss in the primary elastic modulus and no evidence of damage. This observation is consistent with the results from recent in-situ radiographic studies on similar unidirectional composites tested in tension [9].

At load levels corresponding to B, a major through thickness crack was observed. With increasing load levels, additional matrix cracks were seen at regular intervals. This matrix cracking phenomena continued until point C on the stress-strain curve and also resulted in loss of primary elastic modulus. Specimens loaded and unloaded from region CD showed no additional fracture features except better representation of matrix micro cracking. At the ultimate load, point D, specimens broke suddenly.

The general shape of the stress-strain curves for the composites with other fiber contents was similar to that of the composites containing 24 vol% fiber except for the magnitude of the primary elastic modulus, first matrix cracking stress, and ultimate tensile strength values. The fiber content also affected the average matrix crack spacing; that is, as the fiber content increased the average matrix crack spacing decreased as shown in Table I.

TABLE I.- Mean Crack Spacing and First Matrix Cracking Strength for SiC/RBSN composites

Fiber Content, %	Matrix Crack Spacing, mm	First Matrix Cracking Strength, MPa
8 _{+0.5}	2.69 _{+2.12}	128 ₊₂₀
13 _{+0.5}	2.63 _{+1.40}	146 ₊₂₄
16 _{+0.5}	2.52 _{+0.87}	157 ₊₂₄
24 _{+0.5}	1.95 _{+0.61}	224 ₊₂₀

Variation of elastic modulus and first matrix cracking strength with fiber content is plotted in Fig. 3. The hashed region in the figure represents the rule-of-mixtures predicted elastic moduli for the composites based on the following constituent moduli. $E_{SiC}=390$ GPa [10] and $E_{RBSN}=110\pm 10$ GPa [11]. Clearly, the predicted moduli agrees with the measured moduli as both increased linearly up to a fiber content of 24%. However, above this fiber content, the measured moduli leveled off. A similar trend was observed in the Fig. 3 plot of the first matrix cracking stress with fiber content.

As indicated in Fig. 4, the strain to first matrix fracture increased slightly with fiber. This result is consistent with the prediction of deformation models based on fracture mechanics theories [12,13]. It implies that reinforcement of RBSN by large diameter fibers marginally improves its fracture strain and that the strength controlling flaw size is approximately equivalent to fiber diameter. This is in contrast to micro crack bridging mechanism seen in small diameter SiC fiber reinforced glass matrix composites [5,12,13].

Figure. 3 Variation of elastic modulus and first matrix cracking strength with fiber content for SiC/RBSN composites tested in tension.

Figure. 4 Variation of first matrix cracking strain with fiber content for SiC/RBSN composites tested in tension.

The plot of ultimate tensile strength of the composite verses fiber fraction is shown in the Fig. 5. Initially, the ultimate tensile strength increased with fiber fraction to 28% and then the trend reversed. Theoretically both elastic and fracture properties of the composite should increase with increasing volume fraction. Possible reasons for the poor performance of 34% SiC/RBSN are obtained from optical examination of the

Figure. 5 Variation of ultimate strength with fiber content for SiC/RBSN composites tested in tension.

composite cross-sections which show poor infiltration of matrix between the fibers and large matrix voids. The poor load transfer between the fiber and matrix probably also accounts for the lower primary elastic modulus and first matrix cracking strength of these specimens.

Comparison of Figs. 3 and 5 shows that the first matrix cracking strength and ultimate tensile strength values for the composites containing less than 12% fibers were nearly the same, indicating that a minimum fiber fraction of 12% is necessary to achieve stain enhancement advantages of compositing. Composites containing low fiber contents, typically 8% and 12%, fractured into two pieces and the fracture surface (Fig. 6a) showed limited fiber pull out. On the other hand, the fracture surfaces of composites containing 16 to 34 vol% fibers appeared like a broom with little matrix around the fibers (Fig. 6b).

From the matrix crack spacing data shown in Table I, and the elastic property data for the SiC fiber [10] and the RBSN matrix [11], the interfacial shear strength between the fiber and the matrix was measured for 8-34 vol% SiC/RBSN composites using the modified Aveston, Cooper, and Kelly equation [12,14]. The average interfacial shear strength was calculated to be 11 ± 7 MPa.

3.3 Compression Behavior

The room-temperature compression stress-strain curves are shown in Fig. 7 for the unreinforced RBSN and the SiC/RBSN composites containing 24% fiber content. The stress-strain curve for the RBSN displayed essentially a linear region, but that of the

Figure. 6 Fractured tensile specimens showing effects of fiber content: (a) 8 vol%, (b) 24 vol%.

composite showed linearity initially and then became non-linear. From the stress-strain curves of the composites, the primary elastic modulus and ultimate compressive strengths were determined. The plot of the compressive elastic modulus and the ultimate compressive strength with fiber loading is shown in Fig. 8. The hatched region in the figure represents the elastic modulus predicted from the rule-of-mixtures. The measured compressive modulus agrees well with that from the rule-of-mixtures. Comparison of Fig. 3 and Fig. 8 indicates that for a given fiber content of the composite, the measured elastic moduli in compression and in tension are similar. In general, the compressive modulus and ultimate compressive strength increased linearly with fiber content. In contrast, the ultimate compressive strains for composites containing 8-24 vol% fibers remained nearly the same (Fig. 9). Most of the compression specimens failed within the gauge section, and the fractured surface showed broken fibers and crushed matrix (Fig. 10).

To determine the failure mechanism, specimens were unloaded from different load levels up to 95% of the ultimate compressive strength, and then examined under an optical microscope. No evidence of damage was noticed. Some of these specimens that were reloaded to the same load levels indicated no apparent change in elastic modulus. This suggests that final fracture probably occurred due to sudden failure of the matrix, the fiber, or due to buckling of specimen. The fact that the

Figure. 7 The compression stress-strain curve for a 24% SiC/RBSN composite at room-temperature.

ultimate compressive strain of the composites is equivalent to that of the unreinforced matrix suggests that ultimate failure is controlled by matrix failure.

3.4 Bend Behavior

The bend properties of SiC/RBSN composites were found to be a function of L/d , the span to thickness ratio. Figure 11 shows a typical room-temperature stress-strain curve for a 24 vol% SiC/RBSN composite in a 3-point bend test performed at a L/d ratio of 44. Initially the stress varied linearly with strain up to 200 MPa. Beyond this stress level, the stress-strain curve became non-linear and displayed occasional serrations. Deviation from linearity is due to matrix cracks formed normal to the fibers on the tensile surface of the specimen. With increasing stress, the primary crack moved inwards and additional surface cracks were observed. After reaching a maximum load, the specimen failed by ply fracture.

The influence of L/d ratio on the three key properties, namely, the elastic modulus, the first matrix cracking strength, and the ultimate bend strength are shown in Figs. 12 and 13 for 24 vol% SiC/RBSN composite. As the L/D ratio was increased from 10 to 20, the three properties also increased. However, between the L/D ratio of 20 to 44, these properties leveled off.

The failure mode of the composite specimens also depended on L/d ratio. At L/d ratio of less than 20, specimen failure started from shear delamination of the fiber plies. At higher L/d ratio, the failure started typically from a region where tensile stresses are the highest, i.e., on the tensile surface of the

Figure. 8 Variation of modulus and ultimate strength with fiber content for SiC/RBSN composites tested in compression.

Figure. 9 Variation of ultimate strain with fiber content for SiC/RBSN composites tested in compression.

Figure. 10 Typical compression fractured specimen (fiber content 24%).

Figure. 11 The stress-strain behavior in 3-point bending for 24% SiC/RBSN composite ($L/d=44$).

specimen where matrix cracking occurred normal to the fiber. Based on these results, the bend properties of SiC/RBSN depend strongly on L/d ratio. For L/d ratio of more than 20, elastic moduli and first matrix cracking strengths are similar to that measured in tension, suggesting these properties can be evaluated in bend if proper care is a taken.

4. SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The room-temperature mechanical properties of SiC/RBSN composites have been investigated in tension, compression, and bend modes. The major findings are as follows.

Figure. 12 Variation of elastic modulus and first matrix cracking strength with L/d ratio in 3-point bending for 24% SiC/RBSN composites.

Figure. 13 Variation of first matrix cracking strength and ultimate bend strength with L/d ratio for 24% SiC/RBSN composites.

(1) In both tension and compression, composites moduli increased with volume fraction of fibers and were significantly higher than unreinforced matrix of comparable porosity. For the same fiber content, the tension and compression moduli of the composites were nearly the same and can be predictable from rule-of-mixtures.

(2) The first matrix cracking strength of SiC/RBSN composites increased significantly with fiber content, but the matrix cracking strain marginally increased. This shows that increase in first matrix cracking strength with fiber content is due to modulus effect and that matrix microcrack bridging mechanism is non existent in this composite.

(3) The ultimate strength of the composites in tension was controlled by the SiC fibers, but that in compression was controlled by the RBSN matrix.

(4) The bend properties of the composites varied with L/d ratio. For L/d ratio of less than 20, the 24 vol% SiC/RBSN composite failed in shear. Above this L/d value, the composite failure initiated from tensile side of the specimen, giving similar moduli and first matrix cracking strength values as those measured in tension.

5. REFERENCES

1. R.T. Bhatt, ASM International Symposium, 199 (1988).
2. P.J. Lamicq, G.A. Bernhart, M.M. Daucher, and J.G. Mare, Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull., 65 (2), 336 (1986).
3. D.P. Stinton, T.M. Bessman, and R.A. Lowden, Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull., 67 (2), 350 (1988).
4. C.A. Anderson, et al, ASM International Symposium, 209 (1988).
5. K.M. Prewo and J.J. Brennan, J. Mat. Sci., 17 (8), 2371 (1982).
6. R.T. Bhatt, "Method of Preparing Fiber-Reinforced Ceramic Materials," U.S. Patent# 4689188, (1987).
7. J.M. Whitney, I.M. Daniel, and R.B. Pipes, SEM Monograph, #4, (1982).
8. P. Pirouz, et al, in L.C. Dufour, ed., Surfaces and Interfaces of Ceramic Materials, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Netherland, 1989, pp 737.
9. G.Y. Baaklini and R.T. Bhatt, "In-Situ X-Ray Monitoring of Damage Accumulation in SiC/RBSN Tensile Specimens," NASA TM 103733 (1991).
10. J.A. DiCarlo, ASM International Symposium, 1 (1988).
11. R.T. Bhatt and R.A. Phillips, J. Composites Tech. and Research., 12 (1), 13 (1990).
12. J. Aveston, G.A. Cooper, and A. Kelly, "Single and Multiple Fracture," Proceedings of the Conference on the Properties of Fiber Composites, IPC Science and Technology Press Ltd., Surrey, England, 1971, pp. 15.
13. B. Budiansky, J.W. Hutchison, and A.G. Evans, J. Mech. Phys. Solids, 34 (2), 167 (1986).
14. A.C. Kimber and J.C. Keer, J. Mat. Sci. Letters, (1), 353 (1982).

